

“Organization of the passage of mathematics textbooks in elementary grades”

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Annotatsiya: Boshlang‘ich sinflarda matematika darsi, uning xususiyatlari, darsni tshkil qilish tizimi, darsga qo‘yilgan talablar to‘g‘risidagi bilimlarni mustahkamlash.

Kalit so‘zlar: Dars, dars tizimi, dars mazmuni, dars tarkibi, dars tiplari, matematika darslari xususiyatlari, matematika darsi turlari: murakkab dars, yangi materialni o‘rganish darsi, mustahkamlash darsi, umumlashtiruvchi dars, nazorat qilish darslari.

Аннотация: Закрепление знаний об уроке математики в начальных классах, его особенностях, системе организации урока, требованиях к проведению урока.

Ключевые слова: Урок, система урока, содержание урока, содержание урока, виды урока, особенности урока математики, виды урока математики: комплексный урок, урок для изучения нового материала, урок-закрепление, урок-обобщающий, контрольный урок.

Abstract: Strengthening knowledge about the mathematics lesson in primary grades, its features, lesson organization system, requirements for the lesson.

Therefore, it also depends on visual aids, careful selection of active teaching methods, student activity, and the skill level of class students. Another requirement for modern mathematics classes is the development of independent thinking and creative activity of students. The student develops such mental operations as analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, conclusion. The system of mathematics lessons in elementary grades - in each lesson, students work with several concepts. Each of them can be mastered at different stages of this lesson. The understanding of each concept is carried out by repetition, recall of another concept, and this concept serves to explain the following concepts.

In the learning process, each training material is presented in expanded form, this training material is the foundation for understanding the materials taught after it. If we consider the process of mastering another concept, then it is formed as a result of the interconnected teaching of several lessons. Thus, the formation of mathematical concepts is formed not in one lesson, but in the process of passing a series of interrelated lessons. We call such classes a shared class system. Therefore, the teacher must arrange the lessons in a logical sequence that reveals the content of the subject.

The biggest requirement in the structure of the lesson system is to take into account the educational purpose of the lesson, taking into account the methodological and general pedagogical aspects of the principles of teaching. A well-thought-out system of classes on a topic depends on the correct distribution of study time by topic. It should be aimed at developing students' independence by considering specific examples, drawing specific conclusions from them and drawing general conclusions from them. After this knowledge is formed and fixed

in the lesson system, examples and tasks should be solved. After that, it is necessary to develop the skills through exercises, as well as to ensure the continuous integration and generalization of the acquired knowledge. When determining the content of the topic of the program, distributing the material of the topic for class hours, that is, obtaining knowledge, the following main stages are considered.

1. Preparation of new material for training.
2. Perception of new educational material and creation of new knowledge.
3. Consolidation of knowledge and the formation of skills through various exercises.
4. Repetition, generalization and systematization of knowledge.
5. Testing knowledge and skills.

Most of the methodological literature is based on the division of lessons according to their didactic purpose. Below are the types of math lessons:

1. A lesson in mastering new knowledge. In them, students get acquainted with new concepts, calculation methods, solutions to new types of problems, new properties of figures, numbers;
2. A lesson to consolidate knowledge, skills and abilities. They work examples and tasks related to consolidating the knowledge, skills and abilities gained in the previous lesson;
3. Repetition - lessons-generalizations. Examples of this include repetition and debriefing at the end of a particular section, or at the beginning and end of a school year;
4. Lesson control of knowledge, skills and abilities.

5. A mixed or complex lesson in which there are several didactic goals, and all of them are important.

In conclusion, we can say that one of the important requirements of our time is the activation of the knowledge and creative activity of students. Each lesson should focus on thinking and creativity.

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